

Towards Energy-Efficient Split Computing: A Hardware-Software Co-Design Perspective

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Abstract

Edge ML faces resource and energy constraints, requiring optimized split computing, which partitions inference between edge and cloud. We propose a two-phase framework combining offline optimization and dynamic scheduling. It jointly configures split points and hardware settings to balance energy and latency.

1 Introduction

Edge computing provides resources at the network edge, enabling latency-sensitive and privacy-aware applications that often rely on Machine Learning (ML) models for prediction and analytics [4]. This paradigm, known as Edge AI [1], supports smart applications, but faces significant challenges due to the resource and energy constraints of edge devices.

To address these challenges, edge applications can distribute tasks among edge nodes, user devices, and cloud resources [9]. This method keeps latency-sensitive processing at the edge, whilst utilizing the cloud’s scalability. When employing neural networks (NNs) for inference tasks, their layers can be split into multiple sections and executed across edge and cloud based on current needs. This approach, known as split computing [5], can enhance performance by optimizing the use of both edge and cloud strengths.

Effectively implementing split computing is challenging. In fact, selecting split the best points is a complex task due to nonlinear dependencies in the resulting latency and energy usage [3]. Additionally, dynamic runtime conditions in edge environments further increase problem complexity [10]. Finally, both network conditions and hardware characteristics (e.g., CPU tuning via dynamic voltage frequency scaling (DVFS) and hardware accelerators) can significantly impact latency and energy consumption [2, 8].

These factors, combined with the need to satisfy dynamic Quality of Service (QoS) requirements, make jointly optimizing split points and hardware configurations particularly challenging. Addressing these complexities is crucial to enable energy-efficient inference in edge-cloud environments.

2 Proposed Approach

We propose a hardware-software co-design framework for energy-efficient, latency-aware inference in a single edge-cloud setup. It dynamically selects optimal split points and hardware configurations like CPU frequencies and whether to employ hardware accelerators. This method leverages

edge and cloud resources to meet QoS requirements and reduce energy consumption.

Figure 1 illustrates the functionalities of the framework organized in two phases. In the *Offline Phase*, we set up a Multi-Objective Optimization Problem (MOOP) to reduce latency and energy consumption while ensuring inference accuracy. Then, a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm (i.e., NSGA-III) is used to identify a set of non-dominated configurations (i.e., Pareto front solutions). These configurations, precomputed from empirical testing, offer suitable trade-offs across a complex hardware-software parameter space.

During the *Online Phase*, the precomputed configurations are applied dynamically as per incoming requests and QoS needs. The system opts for the most energy-efficient configuration that meets latency demands or, if needed, the quickest one to minimize QoS breaches. This framework adeptly manages varying workloads and network conditions by adjusting edge and cloud parameters in real time.

This two-phase method effectively tackles the complexity of dynamic NN inference in distributed settings. It merges offline optimization with real-time adaptability, reducing energy use, meeting latency needs, and offering a practical solution for present-day edge-cloud inference.

3 Preliminary Results

We evaluated our framework using the VGG16 [7] neural network, a widely used model for computer vision, on a testbed employing a Raspberry Pi 4B, a Google Coral TPU, and a cloud node equipped with an NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU¹. Energy consumption was measured using digital power meters, ensuring more accurate results than estimation-based approaches. We evaluated energy consumption and QoS violations for 50 requests, each consisting of 1,000 inference tasks for reliable measurements. We modeled QoS latency limits as an exponential distribution and compared the results with *edge-only* and *cloud-only* baselines.

Figure 2a displays QoS violations for the baselines and our dynamic configuration approach, shown as violin plots with density and quartiles, with n indicating total violations. The edge-only baseline has high violations, with 25% of requests exceeding latency limits. The cloud-only baseline incurs one

¹Experiments presented in this paper were carried out using the Grid’5000 testbed, supported by a scientific interest group hosted by Inria and including CNRS, RENATER and several Universities as well as other organizations (see <https://www.grid5000.fr>).

Figure 1. An overview of the proposed framework.

Figure 2. Preliminary results for VGG16.

violation. Our dynamic method reduces the violation rate to 4%, with a median exceedance of 10 ms, sustaining QoS.

Figure 2b shows the results of the combined energy consumption of the edge and the cloud. The cloud-only method uses the most energy (median 68 J), while the edge-only method is much more efficient (median <3 J). Our dynamic approach also has a median energy use of <3 J and adapts to QoS, sometimes using up to 72 J.

Summary and Conclusion: Our preliminary results show the potential of dynamic split computing to balance latency and energy efficiency while adapting to variations in workload. Compared to edge-only execution, our approach significantly reduces QoS violations while consuming less energy than cloud-only computation. These findings highlight the need for more experiments to study the full impact of edge-cloud inference, which we already have started including in a pre-print available on arXiv [6].

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by a netidee scholarship. This research has been partially funded through the projects: Transprecise Edge Computing (Triton), Austrian Science Fund (FWF), DOI: 10.55776/ P36870; Trustworthy and Sustainable Code Offloading (Themis), FWF, DOI: 10.55776/ PAT1668223; Satellite-based Monitoring of Livestock in the Alpine Region (Virtual Shepherd), Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG), Austrian Space Applications Programme

(ASAP) 2022 # 5307925; Digital Twin for LoRaWAN Agriculture Systems, Steirische Wirtschaftsförderung (SFG), Ideen!Reich XS 1.000.073.260.

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